

Structural Analysis of News Agency of Nigeria (NAN) in the Digital Era

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20290502>

Abstract

This study analysed the operational and managerial structures of News Agency of Nigeria (NAN) in the digital age, addressing a gap in scholarship that has prioritised functional relevance over organisational structure. Anchored in Institutional Theory and Gatekeeping Theory, the study adopted a qualitative research design. The study population comprised all management staff of NAN, from which twenty-three participants were purposively selected based on their operational and managerial experiences. Data were generated through semi-structured in-depth interviews and analysed using Thematic Analysis following Braun and Clarke's (2021) framework. Findings revealed that NAN operates a centralised managerial system headed by a Managing Director (MD) under Board oversight, supported by a layered editorial hierarchy retained from the analogue era. While this structure strengthens coordination, standardisation and organisational legitimacy, it constrains flexibility for some senior staff. Digital transformation has occurred primarily through functional reconfiguration, with editorial and technical units adopting multimedia production, real-time workflows and digital distribution systems. However, there is imbalance in digital integration; as administrative and marketing units lag behind. Infrastructural constraints and persistent monetisation challenges further complicate adaptation. Altogether, NAN's digital transition reflects institutional layering, embedding new practices within enduring organisational structures in a Global South media context.

Keyword: News Agency of Nigeria (NAN), Digital Transformation, Organisational Structure, Institutional Theory, Gatekeeping Theory, Institutional Layering

Introduction

A news agency, also known as a press or wire service, gathers, processes and distributes verified news to subscribing media houses and institutions rather than publishing it directly to the audiences. A substantial share of routine news content in contemporary newsrooms originates from agency material. This underscores the continued reliance of media organisations on news agencies for timely, accurate and credible information. News agencies also occupy a central position in global news production. They function as

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institutional gatekeepers guided by speed, accuracy and reliability (Vogler *et al* 2024; Chen, 2024).

However, international news flows are dominated by agencies from the Global North, which are often criticised for reinforcing imperialistic perspectives and marginalising the narratives of the Global South (Şkestere, 2025). In response to this imbalance of news flow, many countries in the Global South establish their own news agencies to make the world see happenings around them from their own lenses. Nigeria, as a country in the Global South was not left behind. On the 10th of October 1976, the Nigerian Federal Military Government established News Agency of Nigeria (NAN) through Decree 19. The agency commenced operations in 1978 to serve as Nigeria's official news agency (Babatunde, 2014).

As an institution, a news agency needs well organised operational and managerial structures to function optimally (Bin Hyacinth, Elewodal, Ogwezzy-Ndisika & Suraj, 2025). While previous studies dwelt on the relevance of NAN to global news sourcing, verification and dissemination, with limited attention to the nature of its operations (Babatunde, 2014; Oluodo, 2014), there exists no study on how NAN is structured operationally and managerially. This paper, therefore, analyses the operational and managerial structures of NAN amid digital-era challenges and transformations.

Statement of the Problem

Digitalisation has altered news production, challenging the organisational structures of traditional news agencies. While global agencies have adapted structurally to digital journalism, little is known about how state-owned agencies in the Global South have responded. In Nigeria, the extent to which NAN's operational and managerial structures have adapted to digital realities remains unclear. This, therefore, necessitates the current analysis.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

1. Examine the operational and managerial structures of NAN in the context of the digital age.
2. Assess how these structures support news production, coordination and distribution within Nigeria's contemporary digital media environment.
3. Identify the structural challenges associated with adapting NAN's institutional framework to digital journalism practices.

Conceptual Review

Scholars agree that news agencies are wholesale news organisations that gather, verify, standardise and rapidly distribute raw news to retail media outlets for further processing (Nelissen & Hendrickx, 2023). Their output functions as "information subsidies" that shape newsroom agendas and routines, particularly under time and resource constraints. Through sourcing, translation and editing practices, news agencies also influence news

diversity and the circulation of perspectives across media systems (Vogler *et al* 2024; Nelissen & Hendrickx, 2023).

News agencies are also understood as multi-sided platforms adapting to digital disruption and declining traditional media revenues (Jääskeläinen & Yanatma, 2019). This framework highlights how agencies sustain organisational viability by cross-subsidising core newswire operations through diversified services and institutional markets. Editorial credibility and public trust emerge as strategic assets that support both commercial resilience and continued relevance in competitive digital environments.

Palmer (2019) challenges the notion of news agencies as neutral distributors. He conceptualises them instead as power-laden actors shaped by colonial expansion, war and capitalist competition. He argues that agency routines, norms of objectivity and market dominance influence representation, access and diversity within international communication systems, reinforcing structural hierarchies that privilege certain regions, actors and narratives over others. Similarly, Oso (2020) situates news agencies as central yet often under-recognised actors in global news production. Tracing their nineteenth-century origins, he links their expansion to colonial and commercial interests and distinguishes between international, regional and national agency structures. His analysis foregrounds persistent structural inequalities and ongoing debates over information flow imbalance in the contemporary international news system.

Some studies emphasise how organisational structures, editorial workflows and design competencies interact to support effective digital news delivery (Akça & Çelik Yılmaz, 2023). To maintain credibility, global news agencies institutionalise verification units and platform partnerships to combat disinformation and sustain professional authority (Cazzamatta, 2025). Institutional orientations also shape conflict reporting, producing divergent mediation styles and narratives across agencies (Kozman & Cozma, 2025; Li *et al.*, 2025). While solid operational and managerial structures contribute to organisational success, Apeh and Okoye (2025) identify job satisfaction among workers of NAN as indispensable.

Review of Previous Empirical Studies

Despite the global significance of news agencies, empirical studies that examined NAN as an organisational entity remain limited. Ugwu (2018) contributed to this body of work by investigating the role of Third World news agencies in global news flows, using NAN as a case study. The study, based on a survey of 100 respondents, found that NAN remains relevant in international news dissemination. However, because the focus was on perceived relevance, the study offered limited insight into the internal managerial and operational structures of NAN. This gap, which cannot be scholastically ignored, is what the present study addresses through structural analysis.

Evidence from comparable national contexts reinforces this pattern of relevance without structural interrogation. For instance, Kinoti (2021) examined the Kenya News Agency in a proliferated media environment. Using in-depth interviews with selected media stakeholders alongside documentary analysis, the study found that news agencies remain actively relevant by continuing to perform agenda-setting and coordination roles

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despite intensified competition from digital platforms. Similar to Ugwu (2018), the emphasis remained on relevance and function rather than organisational structure.

Beyond African national news agencies, studies have also extended this relevance-focused inquiry to broader Global South and international contexts. In Yugoslavia, Slaček Brlek (2022) examined the creation of the Non-Aligned News Agencies Pool (NANAP) using archival research and qualitative document analysis. The study found that Yugoslavia promoted South-South news exchange, reduced reliance on Western news agencies and institutionalised “self-reliance” among Non-Aligned Movement (NAM) countries. Nevertheless, the analysis provided limited evidence on newsroom-level routines and content outcomes.

Theoretical Framework

This paper is anchored in institutional theory and gatekeeping theory. Institutional theory explains how organisations, like NAN, sustain their managerial and operational structures under pressures to secure legitimacy (Bennich, 2024). It aligns with this study’s first objective, which is on the existing structures of NAN as well as the institutional constraints shaping NAN’s adaptation to digital journalism practices, as contained in the third objective of this study. Secondly, gatekeeping theory shows how editorial decisions operate across hierarchical newsroom levels (Voinea, 2025). This aligns with the study’s second objective that further clarifies how NAN’s workflow supports coordinated news production and policy-compliant distribution (Akpan, 2024).

Methodology

This paper adopted a qualitative research design to examine the operational and managerial structures of NAN in the digital age. Record obtained from the Human Resources department of NAN as at the time of this study, showed that there are 850 personnel on the agency’s payroll. From this, there are 200 senior management staff, which constitutes the study population. Out of this population, 23 participants were purposive sampled, based on their institutional roles and relevance to this study objectives. Data were generated through semi-structured in-depth interviews, recorded with participants’ consent and transcribed verbatim. The data were analysed using Thematic Analysis, following Braun & Clarke’s (2021) framework. Coding was conducted iteratively to identify patterns relating to managerial authority, editorial hierarchy, digital workflow integration, coordination mechanisms and structural challenges associated with digital adaptation. Ethical principles of informed consent, confidentiality and anonymisation were strictly observed throughout the study.

Findings

Research Question One (RQ1): Operational and Managerial Structures of NAN in the digital age.

Analysis of the interview data showed that NAN operates a centralised managerial authority structure, underpinned by a stable editorial hierarchy and digitally reconfigured operational units.

Managerial Authority and Directorate Structure

Seventeen of the twenty-three respondents described NAN as being headed by a Managing Director/CEO, who exercises executive authority under the policy oversight of a Board of Directors. Decision-making was widely characterised as top-down. As Interviewee 22 explained, *“the agency is headed by the Managing Director who reports to the Board, while directors head the various departments.”* In addition, fourteen respondents explicitly or convergently identified five core directorates: Editorial, Technical, Administration/HR, Finance and Marketing, each headed by a Director corresponding to Level 17 in the Nigerian civil service, reporting directly to the Managing Director. Some respondents (Interviewees 11, 14), however, noted that this level of centralisation limits managerial flexibility.

Editorial Hierarchy and Functional Expansion

Eighteen respondents agreed that NAN has retained its traditional editorial chain of command from the analogue era into the digital age, with the Editor-in-Chief remaining the apex of editorial authority. Interviewee 1 stated that *“the head of editorial operations remains the Editor-in-Chief... down to the reporter at the bottom rung.”* However, five respondents viewed this continuity as rigid, arguing that it constrains innovation and advancement at senior editorial levels. Despite this structural continuity, twenty respondents reported a significant functional expansion of editorial operations, as NAN moved from a text-only wire service to a multimedia organisation. According to Interviewee 5, *“reporters and editors are assigned beats based on their ability to file stories in text, audio, picture and video forms.”* Only three respondents noted implementation imbalance across zones.

Technical Repositioning of Digital Workflow

Nineteen respondents indicated that the technical department has evolved from a support function into a strategic operational core, integrated with editorial processes. Interviewee 3 observed that technology shifted *“from maintenance and support to a strategic and integrated role.”*

Furthermore, twenty-one respondents confirmed a decisive transition from analogue, physically bound workflows to real-time digital production and distribution. The former system of cyclostyled bulletins and dispatch riders has been fully replaced by electronic dissemination. As Interviewee 15 recalled, *“the digital age put a permanent stop to dispatch riders as news products were distributed seamlessly online.”* Only two respondents cited persistent connectivity challenges.

Support Departments and Marketing Adaptation

Digital integration across support units remains unequal. Sixteen respondents observed that administration and human resource functions are still partly analogue. Interviewee 20 admitted that *“we still make use of physical files and cabinets despite access to computers and the internet.”* In contrast, seven respondents reported stronger digital adoption in finance, particularly in electronic payments and subscription management. In marketing, fifteen respondents acknowledged a shift toward digitally mediated client

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management. As Interviewee 4 observed, “revenue collection has become easier as communications and payment demands are seamless.” However, eight respondents argued that marketing digitalisation lags behind editorial and technical transformation, limiting revenue optimisation.

RQ2: How NAN’s Structures support news production and coordination in the digital age

Real-time production and faster internal coordination

Twenty-two of the twenty-three respondents reported that NAN’s current structures support news production primarily through real-time electronic filing, editing and dissemination, replacing the slower analogue routines. Respondents explained that reporters now file stories remotely into central systems, enabling editors to coordinate production without physical movement. As Interviewee 1 stated, reporters can “file their stories to a central pool electronically,” while Interviewee 15 emphasised that distribution is now “seamlessly online,” improving timeliness and workflow continuity.

Multi-layered Gate-keeping Strengthens Coordination Quality Control

Ten respondents described NAN’s coordination as anchored in a multi-layer editorial screening system, from field reporting through zonal/state oversight to headquarters-level editing and final approval. This structure enables standardisation and reduces errors before distribution. Interviewee 4 highlighted the coordinating role of “Line Editors and the control desk... 24/7,” while Interviewee 7 referenced multiple “line editors” before approval, reflecting layered review as an organising principle.

Nationwide Bbureau System Enables Production Reach and Assignment Coordination

Seven respondents stated that NAN’s production capacity and coordination are strengthened by its distributed bureau network, which supports broad coverage and systematic assignment flow. Interviewee 1 traced this to state and zonal supervision structures, while Interviewees 14 and 22 similarly emphasised national spread and coordination through departments/directorates. This network was repeatedly framed as a competitive advantage for gathering geographically diverse news quickly.

Technical and Platform Systems Support Subscriber Coordination and Delivery

Seven respondents explicitly linked coordination to technical distribution systems, satellite, portals, websites, and related platforms, which facilitate fast delivery to subscribers. Interviewee 2 described the satellite broadcast network as enabling subscribers to receive content “as soon as they are edited,” while Interviewee 12 noted that editors/reporters are “configured on a portal,” and Interviewee 3 stressed tighter technical, editorial integration to optimise delivery systems.

Training and Partnership Support Production Standardisation

Eight respondents indicated that training, often supported by collaborations with foreign agencies and partners, helps align staff capacity with digital routines. This improves coordination across desks and formats. Interviewee 5 cited training exposures through agencies such as Reuters/Xinhua, Interviewee 15 linked multimedia transition to structured training opportunities, and Interviewee 22 noted that staff possess “basic digital skills,” though advanced skills remain uneven.

Constraint Affecting Production Coordination

Although coordination has improved, sixteen respondents identified constraints that weaken how structures support production, especially funding, electricity/internet instability, and imbalance of infrastructure across state/zonal offices. Interviewee 12 cited “lack of stable power” and “no internet connectivity” in some locations, Interviewee 3 linked coordination pressures to infrastructure deficits, and Interviewee 20 reported that some internal support functions remain partly analogue, limiting organisational efficiency.

RQ3: Impact of digital transformation on content production, distribution and revenue at NAN

Digital Expansion of Content Production

Twenty-one respondents agreed that digital transformation shifted NAN from a text-only wire service to a multimedia news organisation that produces text, photographs, audio

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and video. This expansion was repeatedly linked to newsroom restructuring and the creation of multimedia units. As Interviewee 1 explained, NAN moved “*from a text-only organisation... to a multimedia agency,*” while Interviewee 15 noted that the establishment of studios and multimedia services “*placed it in the league of international multimedia news agencies.*”

Real-time and Remote Newsroom Operations

Twenty respondents reported that digitalisation enabled real-time reporting and remote production. It has replaced fixed bulletin schedules and location-bound workflows. Reporters now file stories electronically from the field, while editors process content without physical presence in the newsroom. Interviewee 3 observed that reporters and editors can now work “*virtually... as long as they have internet connectivity.*” This has also improved speed and output significantly.

Transformation of Distribution Systems

Twenty-two respondents identified distribution as the most transformed operational area. Analogue systems such as dispatch riders, telex, and cyclostyled bulletins have been replaced by satellite transmission, portals, websites and social media platforms. Interviewee 2 stated that subscribers now receive content “*as soon as they are edited,*” while Interviewee 12 noted that stories are “*pushed straight to subscribers through the portal,*” expanding reach and immediacy.

Revenue Diversification and Digital Services

Seventeen respondents indicated that digital transformation expanded NAN’s revenue streams beyond traditional subscriptions. New income sources include multimedia packages, photo services, online subscriptions, advertising, training and event-related media services. Interviewee 15 described the creation of NAN Bizcom as enabling the agency to “*engage in enterprises... advantageously carried out,*” while Interviewee 3 linked improved speed and quality to greater client willingness to pay.

Persistent Monetisation Challenges

Despite these gains, fourteen respondents cautioned that digitalisation has not resolved NAN’s revenue constraints. Key challenges include content leakage to non-subscribers, competition from free online platforms and reliance on government subvention. Interviewee 3 captured this tension succinctly, noting that “*NAN clients are equally its competitors,*” while Interviewee 22 emphasised difficulties in enforcing payment for digital content.

Summary Assessment

Collectively, respondents agreed that digital transformation has enhanced production capacity, accelerated distribution and widened revenue opportunities, while exposing structural weaknesses in monetisation and sustainability. As Interviewee 18 remarked,

digitisation has reinforced newsroom confidence in “wait for NAN report,” even as economic viability remains unbalanced.

Discussion

This study examined the operational and managerial structures of the News Agency of Nigeria (NAN) in the digital age, extending earlier research that focused primarily on relevance rather than organisational structure. The findings indicate that NAN’s digital transition is characterised by institutional continuity combined with functional adaptation, producing both coordination strengths and structural constraints. The persistence of a centralised managerial hierarchy reflects strong institutional stability. From the perspective of Institutional Theory, such continuity aligns with organisations’ tendency to preserve established structures to maintain legitimacy and regulatory conformity (Bennich, 2024). Empirically, this finding converges with Ugwu (2018), who identified NAN’s enduring relevance in global news flows. However, the present study extends Ugwu’s work by showing that this relevance is structurally sustained through a top-down administrative model. At the same time, minority concerns about rigidity suggest that institutional persistence can constrain flexibility and adaptive capacity, confirming Bennich’s (2024) caution that stability may limit responsiveness in changing environments.

The retention of a layered editorial hierarchy further underscores NAN’s reliance on structured gatekeeping. Consistent with Gatekeeping Theory, editorial decisions continue to pass through sequential organisational levels, ensuring coordination, standardisation, and policy compliance (Voinea, 2025). This finding converges with Kinoti (2021), who observed that national news agencies retain agenda-setting and coordination roles despite digital disruption. However, while Kinoti focused on functional relevance, the present study reveals the internal gatekeeping architecture through which coordination is enacted. Minority perceptions that the hierarchy slows

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innovation reflect Voinea's (2025) argument that traditional gatekeeping structures face increasing tension under digital speed logics.

Digital transformation within NAN emerged primarily as functional reconfiguration rather than structural overhaul. Editorial and technical units have adopted multimedia production and real-time workflows while the organisational framework remains intact. This pattern aligns with Kinoti (2021), who noted operational adaptation without abandonment of legacy structures. The present study contributes further by demonstrating uneven digital integration, as administrative and marketing units lag behind editorial and technical departments, an internal asymmetry not addressed in earlier empirical studies.

Coordination remains supported by NAN's nationwide bureau system, reinforcing earlier conclusions that national agencies function as central nodes in domestic news ecosystems (Ugwu, 2018; Kinoti, 2021). However, this study diverges by foregrounding infrastructural constraints, particularly electricity and internet instability, which mediate coordination in practice. Interpreted through Akpan (2024), these findings highlight the contextual limits of gatekeeping in Global South media environments, where organisational routines are shaped by bureaucratic and material conditions.

Finally, while digitalisation has expanded NAN's revenue opportunities, persistent monetisation challenges remain. Earlier empirical studies did not address revenue structures directly, making this a key extension of the literature. In comparative perspective, Slaček Brlek (2022) emphasised collective strategies for institutional self-reliance among non-aligned agencies, whereas the present study reveals internal market tensions within a national agency operating in a competitive digital environment.

The findings suggest that NAN's digital transition reflects a process of institutional layering, in which new digital practices are embedded within enduring managerial authority and editorial gatekeeping structures. This configuration enhances coordination and output while exposing persistent tensions related to rigidity, infrastructural inequality and revenue sustainability. By integrating empirical comparison with Institutional and Gatekeeping theories, the study demonstrates that organisational structure remains central to understanding digital adaptation in Global South news agencies.

Conclusion

This study examined the operational and managerial structures of NAN in the digital age and found that digital adaptation has occurred largely through functional reconfiguration within enduring institutional frameworks. While centralised authority and hierarchical gatekeeping continue to support coordination, credibility and nationwide coverage, uneven digital integration, infrastructural constraints, and fragile monetisation remain significant challenges. Altogether, NAN's digital transition reflects institutional layering, combining stability with selective transformation in response to contemporary journalism demands.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations are hereby given:

1. Introduce measured decentralisation: Greater operational autonomy should be granted to zonal and departmental heads to improve flexibility and speed, while retaining central policy oversight.
2. Rationalise editorial workflows: Editorial gatekeeping processes should be streamlined to reduce unnecessary layers, particularly for routine digital content, without compromising quality control.
3. Complete organisation-wide digital integration: Administrative, finance, and marketing units should be fully integrated into digital systems to address internal asymmetries and improve efficiency.
4. Strengthen infrastructural support across bureau: Targeted investment in power supply, internet connectivity and digital equipment at state and zonal offices is necessary to enhance coordination and productivity.
5. Enhance revenue protection and monetisation mechanisms: NAN should strengthen content protection, subscription enforcement, and digital service packaging to reduce revenue leakage and improve sustainability.
6. Institutionalise continuous digital training: Regular capacity-building programmes should be implemented to ensure that staff across departments can effectively engage with evolving digital journalism practices.

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